

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF TEACHING A LANGUAGE IN THE CLASSROOM AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract:

There are a number of issues that every language teacher faces while teaching a certain language in the classroom. This article gives information about the actual problems of teaching a language in the classroom and several effective steps which can be taken to tackle with these issues.

Key words: problems, teaching methods, classroom, students, teachers, challenges, educators, language

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Nowadays, there has been significant transformations, posing numerous challenges to educators around the world. Although teaching is hard work, being a language teacher might be the most difficult job among other professions. Here a number of specific issues that all language teachers have to handle and work through as well as some proposed solutions to tackle with these problems.

1. Classroom management. One of the most prominent difficulties of language teaching is noisy atmosphere in the classroom. In other words, ensuring that all students stay on the task and work in a calm manner can be challenging for educators. In every language classroom, there is always a student who seems to be determined to make teaching as difficult as possible for the teachers; thus, handling those students requires skill and experience. Below, the solutions to this problem will be counted:

Creating classroom rules together with students.

"One of the most effective and practical ways teachers can give students a say in the classroom is by allowing them to participate in developing the classroom rules or behavior guidelines.", says Jonathan Erwin the author of the book *Classroom of Choice*. Indeed, holding a class discussion at the start of a new year or semester and allowing students to have a say in their learning environment suggests that educators value their thoughts. Teachers can discuss with them for example how to treat each other, how they would like to be treated, in which circumstances mobile phones and other devices are allowed during class, and so on. Rather than being the passive receiver, students are now given the power and freedom to shape their classroom instead of being just told what and when to learn.

Grouping students.

When teachers group students for a task, it is not an invitation for chaos but, in fact, engagement. Belonging to a group and working collaboratively with

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members means support from and a sense of responsibility for the group. Working as a group to complete the given task or sharing ideas with another group requires each members' participation and contribution. Therefore, students are less likely to engage in off-task conversation. The desire or competition for honor boosts their engagement in the task and group cohesiveness.

Building rapport with students and earn authority.

Educators argued that balancing warmth and strong boundaries is key to the success of a teacher-student relationship. Taking them as your children and loving them unconditionally but being consistent and flexible by holding them accountable are important factors to establish a healthy and positive relationship [1].

Praising the students.

Research studies revealed that students in every grade and all subjects like to be praised for their work. Even as an adult, praise from professors or the boss could make my whole day brighter. Given the identified positive effects of teacher praise, teachers should try to make better use of this tool. Effective praise should be connected with a particular behavior or process which serves as the reason for praise in a manner as timely as possible. The sooner the feedback is received, the better and longer-lasting impact it has. Teachers can use praises like:

I can definitely see how hard you have worked on this task/assignment

I see how difficult this problem is to solve and how much time and effort you have put into solving it

I am so proud of the work effort you have put

You have learned so much that this assignment might not have been that challenging for you, so let's try and find something new and interesting next time that will help you learn even more

Involving parents.

Understanding the family's culture and the relationships between parents and the child help teachers support students' well-being and development. The family is always the first teacher and is central to the development of the child. Time and effort are of course required to get to know your students' parents .

Motivate students with gamified approach and with educational technology.

Many teachers have agreed to this: "nothing makes the teacher's life as easy as sparking their students' motivation to learn". Think about it yourself: when you were in school, were you easier to manage when you were truly motivated to learn and interested in the task at hand? Teachers can always incorporate gamified aspects to the traditional physical classroom by using board games or using different educational technology tools. Modern digital native students might even expect that technology would be leveraged better in schools and in their learning environment.

2. Complications in a language learning process. While teaching a language, educators usually need to have a native speaker's fluency. However, acknowledging this kind of skill may be time consuming and complicated, which can result in additional, mental and physical pressure on tutors. The solutions to this issue would be followings:

Implementation of various methods while teaching.

The teacher may apply a number of teaching methods including Communicative language teaching (CLT) or Direct method. This approaches are probably now the most popular teaching model for English language teaching globally. In part because they aim at putting students in a variety of real-life

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situations, so that they can learn how to use their language skills to communicate in the real world. Educators, therefore, tend to focus on fluency of communication rather than accuracy and lessons are more hands-on than theoretical.

Interactive and relevant classroom activities characterize this approach along with the use of authentic source materials. Teachers are encouraged to provide the students with as much opportunity to give and receive meaningful communication as possible. The use of personal experience is also common in CLT classrooms.

3. Teaching students of different abilities in the same class

Ideally, students would be in a language class with other students at the same ability level. Unfortunately, that's not always possible or practical and teachers often face teaching students at very different points on their language learning journey. Inevitably this means that it can be difficult to pitch lesson content correctly as for some, it's too hard and for others it's too easy.

As a solution to this problem, it can be stated that to keep students on track, it is, therefore, vital for educators to identify the level of proficiency each student currently has. Most informal language teaching institutions will offer students a CEFR test (the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) at the beginning of their course. Once teacher know if students are basic, independent or proficient language learners, they can then develop a personalized and tailored plan to help them to achieve their goals and potential.

All in all, if above-mentioned problems are tackled with these suggested ways, it is truth-worthy to say that being a language teacher is considered as a rewarding job that genuinely helps to transform the levels of students.

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